

OF THE PRINCIPAL LEXEMA IN UZBEK AND TURKISH LANGUAGES

Feruzha Rahmatova

A doctoral student at Tashkent State University of Uzbek
Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi
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ANNOTATION

Somatisms are nouns that literally mean human or animal body parts . The term "somatism" used in linguistics for the names of human body parts was first used by the scientist F. Bakk, who studied Estonian phraseology. He expressed the opinion that "somatisms belong to one of the oldest layers of phraseology and constitute the most used part of the vocabulary of any language" [FOVakk 1964] . And D. Bazarova conducted a number of scientific researches devoted to the comparison of somatisms of Turkic languages. AM Kochevatkin's " Somaticheskaya lexicon c dialect Erzyanskogo yazyka ", AV Prozhilov's " Somaticheskie cost human i ix Yazykovaya ontology c sovremennom German yazyke ", Timea Chete's " Somaticheskie phraseology c ruskom i Hungarian somatisms were analyzed in various aspects in his scientific work " yazykax ".

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a number of scientific works, somatisms have been studied within the framework of phraseologisms. Most of the scientific works on somatisms in the Uzbek language are devoted to the study of somatic phraseological units . A. Isayev in his research "Somatic Phraseological Units of the Uzbek Language" (1976) studied somatisms from the point of view of their synonyms, antonyms, homonyms and the communicative function of the language. In the study , phraseological units with "head" and "eye" components were compared in the Tatar, Turkmen and Azerbaijani languages . Sh. R.Usmonova studied the lexical-semantic and grammatical structure of somatic phraseology in the scientific work "Somatic phraseology in the Uzbek and Turkish languages" (1998). Many scientific works have been carried out in this regard in the Turkish language as well . Scientists who have studied the somatic phraseologisms of Turkic languages show that the word "head" is the most active soma in the formation of a phrase . For example, while T. Aktash gave information about phrases and their fields in his dissertation work, S. Nekiy Isenbet's work entitled "Tatar Tëllëññ Phrezëologic Süzëğë" expressed 2468 names of "head" and 18 organs related to "head". defined phrases. [Aktas, 2013]. At the same time, there are scientific works written on this subject in other Turkic languages , and some of them are devoted to the comparative analysis of these linguistic units in two Turkic languages.

Although a number of scientific works devoted to the study of somatic phraseologisms have been carried out , there are no in-depth monographic studies carried out on the polysemantic properties of somaticisms, the methods of transfer of meaning in them. In this article, we will consider the phenomenon of ambiguity in the somatisms of the Uzbek and Turkish languages using the example of the lexeme "head". For this purpose, we selected 10

classic and modern works created in the Uzbek and Turkish languages and determined the meanings of the word "bas" in these works and the methods of transfer of meaning.

who are brothers with us and have harmony in our cultures, values, and language, metaphorical and metonymic interests and is to study the relationship between languages, language behavior. The results of the study can provide a good opportunity to determine the cultural code of the language, to eliminate the problems that arise in the process of Turkish-Uzbek translation, and to create a somatic field in electronic dictionaries created in computer linguistics.

Somatisms in our language are the main lexical elements of the language from the semantic point of view. Etymologically, the names of body parts embody nature, society, and the specific features of life at that time. The historical and modern forms and dialects of the Uzbek language attract attention. From the point of view of the language and behavior of Uzbek speakers, it is important to take into account how somatisms appear in the sources when defining the language system. As mentioned, somatisms are the oldest and at the same time the most active lexical layer in the history of the language. Their activity creates polysemy. The multiplicity of somatic units is directly related to people, their perception of the world, and their relation to reality. Taking advantage of somatisms, a person re-embodies a unique world view in his thinking. This is reflected in the high use of somatic units in a person's speech. In the process of researching the semantic content of somatic units, it is found that their field of application is quite wide, in proverbs, phraseology, as well as figurative. It can be recognized that it is active in opening a social. **On the example** of the word "head", we will consider the feature of ambiguity in somatisms. **In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language**, 20 meanings of the word "Bosh" are given. The main word is the most used somatism in the Turkish language. In the explanatory dictionary of the Turkish language, 16 meanings of the word (bas) are given.

1. The front (in humans, animals) part of the body above the neck; the head

-- The wolf wrestler walked around the cemetery. He was shaking his head. (T. Murad "Stars burn forever")

-- The rider sitting in the saddle flew over the head of the horse and fell under the feet of other horses. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- Mingbashi asked, pulling his horse's head back. (Cholpon "Night and Day")

-- Kholmatjon, full of blue orders, was smiling next to Dildor, who had a net on his head. (S. Ahmad "Ufq")

-- A headscarf he took it and threw it next to him. - Work is getting delayed, aunt! (O'. Hoshimov "Between Two Doors")

-- He was sitting with his head raised high and staring at the moon, carelessness was visible on his face.

2. Consciousness, brain;

-- The future child is known from the beginning. (proverb)

-- Inim Yolchi, you have a golden head. (Oybek "Kutlug' blood")

-- Why didn't this idea come to me earlier? (O'. Hoshimov "World affairs")

3. Chief, leader;

-- Do you understand? Be your own boss. Dry out in order. Don't rush, measure seven and cut one. (T. Murad "Stars burn forever")

-- Such an aspirant Chori wrestler used to rub shoulders with Temir wrestler, took him to weddings and taught him some of his trades! . (T. Murad "Stars burn forever")

-- It was one of Babur's strongest dreams to ascend the throne one day and fight victoriously at the head of all the begs. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- Hazrat Alisher used to say: " A child who becomes a child becomes a leader at the age of fifteen, a person who does not become a child becomes a youth at the age of forty." (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

, Ikromjan wanted to let this boy live and be the head of his children. (S. Ahmad "Ufq")

-- He took it upon himself to be the head of the rice harvest. (S. Ahmad "Ufq")

4. Position, senior, senior position;

-- The chairman of the collective farm became the chief bakovul . (T. Murad "Stars burn forever")

-- They recognize you as our chief ruler! Let 's pay the death penalty! Stop the war , my lord! (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

"Who will be the commander-in-chief should be decided by the honorable brothers and sisters themselves," he said. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

5. Huge, big, main;

-- Brothers, we are not heating up the main plate . (T. Murad "Stars burn forever")

--Here is the main gate of Khorezm. (i. Jabborov . The secret of old ruins)

6. The most important, main, leader;

--If we determine the main task before us ... (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- In the character of the main character Bazarov, the writer embodied such qualities as superstition and striving for innovation. (O'. Hoshimov "Works of the World")

-- In the first one, a person can preserve the innate noble qualities, but in absence, no one can preserve them", one of the characters in the work explains this statement to the main character based on real life examples. (O'. Hoshimov "Works of the World")

"That's the main reason I came to you!" Hasanali said. (A. Qadiri "The past days")

7. The earliest, the first; chief child, chief bride.

-- The first part of the word, ghaliban, was said inside. (Cholpon "Night and Day")

a Russian writer famous for his works promoting moral corruption at the beginning of the 20th century . (Cholpon "Night and Day")

-- The forehead bone hit Tahir's hand as hard as a stone, his thumb snapped, and a sharp pain went to his brain. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

--His thumb was swollen, the pain was unbearable when he moved it . (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- He held the niche between his thumb and forefinger . (T. Murad "Stars burn forever")

-- From the beginning of the line, he raised the description of the khan to the heights and began to write: "Hazrat Imam Zaman, Caliph Rahman"... (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

8. Man, person (move);

--One death for one head (proverb)

-- At that time, heads with scarves appeared over the wall : women looked around. . (T. Murad "Stars burn forever")

-- What did this head not see when he came into the world ? (A. Qadiri "The past days")

9. In the account of livestock, each animal. (with counted numbers) one cow, three sheep;

-- The barn belonging to Ahmed Niyazimbetov, a resident of Ellikkala village, Ellikkala District, Republic of Karakalpakstan, with 440 sheep and goats burned down for unknown reasons. (from newspaper)

-- While Uzbekistan has 140 cows per thousand people, there are only 40 cows in the USA, 44 cows in Great Britain, and 45-48 cows in the European Union countries. (Internet)

10. The top, end, peak of vertical things ;

- From the cane on the roof It is cold when the yellow sumac hangs down and the harvest begins

At the peak, winter returned . (O. Hoshimov "Between Two Doors")

--When the geese landed on the top of the mountain, he tricked his child by saying that "that goose" had come - to the mayor

he listened to the sound of the birds for a while and said " no ", barely moving his puckered lips.

(U.Azim "Goose")

-- Mulberry hat on the head. (S. Ahmad "Ufq")

- Begum, the top of the mountain is not without snow , the head of the young man is safe. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

--Togora at the beginning of the roof, Zogora on the roof... (From folk songs)

-- If there is a shortage at home , don't eat it, make a double oven on the roof (proverb)

11. The occurrence of a ceremony, event, incident , the beginning of the process of realization

stage;

-- Well, you 're on your way, wrestler! he said. Tilovberdi wrestler walked ahead. Abray followed suit. (T. Murad. "Stars burn forever")

-- We..." This word "we" has been repeated a lot since the beginning of the investigation. (Cholpon "Night and Day")

--Until the beginning of work (proverb)

-- Why in most cases, at the beginning of the wedding, the chairmen of citizens' self-governing bodies or community advisers on religious and educational affairs do not appear? (from newspaper)

12. Side, front, side;

-- He gathered people at the head of Risolat and kept shouting. (S. Ahmad "Ufq")

-- to Masha's sigh despite this, Ergashali kept fighting over his brother's head a mine fell on his friends and tore ten people to pieces. (O. Hoshimov "Between Two Doors")

-- But reasonable Don't try to bite the fascist, rolling in the snow and howling .

my father has slaughtered under it own one German who is dying like a sheep knowing how to see with my own eyes

I killed you I really wanted to laugh at the beginning.

(O. Hoshimov "Between Two Doors")

--Rais, who was constantly approaching the workers, began to shout again. (from the newspaper)

-- What kind of day did the poor old woman who left her child to the plague and let the goose fly? (U.Azim "Goose")

13. The upper side of a bed, bed, etc., where the head rests ; the place above the waist of a person lying in such a position;

-- Kneeling at the head of the grave , he recited the blessing. Under his feet, a blanket rubs the marble slab. (T. Murad. "Stars burn forever")

--Haji came to Kumush and sat down . (A. Qadiri "The past days")

-- Then, at the head of his mother's grave... he saw a white marble ! (T. Murad. "Stars burn forever")

-- A shelf made of fragrant sandalwood was placed at the head of the bed, and his father's poetic divan stood alone on a separate shelf of the shelf. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

--When he woke up in the morning , Umrinisabibi, one of the neighboring women, was sitting at his head. (Cholpon "Night and Day")

14. Combined with some nouns, it means the thing expressed by this noun itself or its location, surroundings;

-- He was pouring tea into the teapots in front of the stove after collecting the seats and preparing the breakfast places : - There is no sign of my father, is there? he asked his mother. (Cholpon "Night and Day")

the table, waiting for Zebi to make tea Salty, who was sitting , saw this situation through the door with both wings open, got up and went to his friend. (Cholpon "Night and Day")

15. Long , continuous, tall things, place, starting place or end of areas, skirt; one of the two ends, edge, side of such things;

-- As soon as the guests left at the beginning of the street , the elder Nabi gave a voice. (T. Murad. "Stars burn forever")

-- Kneeling at the head of the grave , he recited the blessing. Under his feet, a blanket rubs the marble slab.

(T. Murad. "Stars burn forever")

-- We don't have grain fields. Now Hayrondara is a cotton field from head to toe... The watermen who are drawing water at the beginning of Rakhtazor say, let there be a way. (T. Murad. "Stars burn forever")

-- In the distance, at the beginning of a village street that has turned into a bonfire german

The last truck was dragging and slipping in the snow . (O' .

Hoshimov "Between Two Doors")

16. The starting place, time, beginning, introduction of an event, event , period or season, work, text, etc.;

-- They looked at each other from head to toe . (T. Murad. "Stars burn forever")

-- So learn the laws of jurisprudence from beginning to end. I will take the photo. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- From the beginning of the line, he raised the description of the khan to the heights and began to write: "Hazrat Imam Zaman, Caliph Rahman"... (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- Perhaps there is a grace of God Almighty, he gave me a new life." Khondamir was surprised that Babur wrote so openly about his life . (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- In order to hear advice from women, especially a proposal from his wife, Razzaq Sufi would have to come from the beginning again . (Cholpon "Night and Day")

-- The words consisted of Miryakub's strange questions at the beginning: (Cholpon "Night and Day")

-- The first part of the word , ghaliban, was said inside. (Cholpon "Night and Day")

-- There is a strange sentence at the beginning of the letter, you did not pay attention . (Cholpon "Night and Day")

-- The beginning of the week is the hardest time. (Internet)

17. What is the pretext for the beginning of an event, event, etc., the initial cause;

--The beginning of my charm is the beginning of my quarrel. (proverb)

--Looking for happiness at someone else's doorstep is the beginning of unhappiness. (A. Qahhor "Aching teeth")

--But the beginning of the problem is that most driving schools don't even have a training car

18. Head-shaped fruit, fruit of some plants;

--One day late in the afternoon, Tahir brought three or four heads of white raisins to the vineyard. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- Babur was happy and took a head of grapes got hold of it . Although the white raisin that was grown for the first time in the history of these lands is a little more dry , its taste reminded Babur of Samarkand. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

19. Karra, account. (in numbers)

-- To get four heads.

-- Pay five heads .

20. The 3rd person is used as an auxiliary with the addition of the possessive suffix and the place-time agreement, exit agreement;

think about the calamities that will befall the people , I regret that today's rains did not turn into a flood and wash away that bridge. (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

-- Perhaps there is a grace of God Almighty, he gave me a new life." Khondamir was surprised that Babur wrote so openly about his life . (P. Kadirov "Starry Nights")

The main word is the most used somatism in the Turkish language. The explanatory dictionary of the Turkish language provides information about the following meanings of the polysemous word Baş (head) .

1. Head; In humans and animals, the part that covers organs such as the brain, eyes, ears, nose, and mouth, located on the top or front of the body, head, head. [the upper or front part of the body where parts such as the neck, eyes, nose, and mouth of humans and animals are located;] A woman with a white forehead and black eyes was standing in front of us with a headscarf tied to her mouth; A big wounded wolf is sitting on his hind legs; a terrible, long head was staring into my eyes with fiery eyes.

2. A person who manages a community. [chief, leader;] And the soldiers walked with a fennel made of thorns and put it on their head and dressed the mother in a robe. The mind is not old, it is in the head. Just yesterday, the children were cut off from us by a chief and a manager. Chief Engineer Harry Scott opened his eyes when he heard this.

3. The beginning . First of all, we need to talk about what we mean by deception.

One of the things we miss in a relationship is trying to completely change the person on the other side or trying to mold them into the mold that suits you.

4. Temel, esas .[asos, tamal;] According to Adeetä, Kurog placed a man-godlike structure, an idol, on the main wall of the country, and all of them bowed their heads. Depression is one of the most common psychological diseases today.

5. Arazide en yüksek nokta .[the highest part of the steep things, the tip;] On both sides of the road, there are mountains whose heads are as high as the sky, and their tops are covered with pine trees like two green walls; the peaks are as white as milk...

6. The common end of something . Is it easy, thirty-nine years bent at the table, this back was bent. Both ends of the street were filled with our party members

7. One of the ends of something . [beginning or end of long things, places] In a beautiful autumn mood, the poet sat like he was lying by the pool, güneşleniyordu. One policeman at one end of the street, another policeman at the other end, are constantly shouting: Nails were hammered into the radio box, the heads of three of the nails were sticking out and curled.'

8. Grain in farm animals and some foods. [animal or vegetable grain] Twenty heads. Ten heads of cattle. Three onions. his head is a pumpkin, long hair, a little gray, a green hat

9. Surcharge given or received when changing money , sarrafiye .

10. The vicinity or surroundings of something . Basarbek, a head of the army, a horse, a horse, a soldier, a soldier, hem kıpır, nicä Külen kocasının war derileri germää kurusunnar; the heads of divisions are commanders of army divisions; For twenty-five years, I lived at the head of the table, outside of war, in peace without knowing anything about it.

is a pronoun that means "one's own being " . She was working and taking care of her child alone.

12. The most important, the most important, the most advanced in terms of management, the most important , the leading;] Confucius put the "reliable apple" at the top of the list of characteristics that make a person successful. The general director of "International Hyster Corp." also assigned the task of finding out the reasons for the complaints from Turkey to the engineer Harry Scott, who is the head of the technical experts who will go to Turkey.

13. The highest of the five ranks of wrestlers in wrestling .

14. "... per se" comes after the nouns and before the word of quantity and gives the meaning of multiplication . When Beybaba was making a chicken, he lowered the cut to his thumb saying that he was hitting a nail.

15. The front side of sea boats . [front on a sea boat;]

16. En uç, yüksek nokta veya en ön .

of the word " Bosh " in the Uzbek and Turkish languages in the table below:

In Uzbek language	Meanings of the word head	In Turkish
human head A horse's head	1. The front (in humans, animals) part of the body above the neck; head	The head of the name is the head of a man
Man with his head.	2. Consciousness, brain;	The mind is not old, it is in the head
To be the head	3. Chief, leader;	the head of the army
Prosecutor General, Chief Physician	4. Position, senior, senior position;	chief engineer
Grand prize	5. Huge, big, main;	the main table is the

		main wall of the country
The main reason Head talk	6. The most important, main, leader;	--
chief child, chief bride	7. The earliest, the first;	--
One death per head	8. Man, person (move);	a head with long yellow hair
Three heads of sheep	9. Each animal in the livestock account. (with counted numbers)	ten head of cattle
The top of the mountain	10. The top, end, peak of vertical things ;	mountains whose heads touch the sky
The beginning of the work	1111. The first stage in the process of the occurrence of a remony, event, event;	Head of the world
Go to the head of the workers	12. Side, front, side;	--
The head of the bed.	13. The upper side of a bed, bed, etc., where the head is placed; the place above the waist of a person lying in such a position;	--
The head of the furnace Head of the table	14. Combined with some nouns, it means the thing expressed by this noun itself or its surroundings;	pool head
The head of the river The beginning of the road	15. Long, continuous, tall things, place, starting place or end of fields, skirt; one of the two ends, edge, side of such things;	garbage head the boat the head
The beginning of the story The beginning of the year	16. The starting place, time, beginning, introduction of an event, event, period or season, work, text, etc.;	the beginning of diseases
The beginning of the conflict	17. What is the pretext for the beginning of an event, event, etc., the initial cause;	--
Head cabbage	18. The head-shaped fruit of some plants;	three onions

To pay in ten heads	19. Karra, account. (in numbers)	--
With a widow's head With a woman's head	20. The 3rd person is used as an auxiliary with the additions of the possessive suffix and the place-time agreement, exit agreement;	from head to toe
--	or received when changing money, sarrafiye.	

Result and Conclusion

All people of the world, of any nationality, know what names are given to the head, feet, eyes, ears and other body parts of their body . Somatisms represent the concepts and relations necessary in any human society, without which it is difficult to imagine the speech of people, and the somatic vocabulary is characterized by the speed of use and developed polysemy . According to the results of the analysis , the word "head" is very active in both languages and has many meanings. The semantic features of the Turkish and Uzbek languages, which have similarities in their ethnographic formation, culture, and traditions, have commonalities and similarities. This is also reflected in subtleties of meaning in the use of somatisms . We have seen that the head word has polysemantic features in 20 places in Uzbek and 16 places in Turkish. In the process of translation, the four meanings of the Uzbek language can be expressed through phrases and expressions in the Turkish language. We used 10 works of art in the comparative analysis, which may not reveal the national color of the Uzbek and Turkish languages and all the subtleties of meaning .

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